

Soil and Wastewater Characteristics in Oil-Polluted Environment of Egbema, Southeast, Nigeria

Obiechefu G. C¹., Emerson K. U^{2*}., Ohaji E. C³., Ehumadu C. N¹., Ibeh V. C³., Etumnu M. C¹.

¹Department of Agricultural and Biosystems Engineering, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria

²Department of Agricultural Engineering, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

³Department of Civil Engineering, University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Umuagwo, Imo State, Nigeria

**Corresponding author: kemerson@hotmail.co.uk*

Received: September 4, 2024; Accepted: September 18, 2024; Published: September 19, 2024

Doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13789305>

Abstract: Oil-producing activities often lead to pollution and damage to the ecosystem, when they are not managed properly. The Egbema community has witnessed significant pollution of its soil and water resources as a result of oil-producing activities of oil companies and illegal bunkers. This study aims to determine the level of soil contamination from oil-producing activities and the wastewater quality discharged into nearby water-body. Soil and wastewater samples were collected using standard procedures. Soil samples were collected in duplicate from four locations in a randomized design, and wastewater from two identified point-sources. Samples were transported to the laboratory in ice-packed container, for analysis. Both soil and wastewater are acidic with pH <5.5 Heavy metals were present in varying proportions in soil and wastewater samples. Lead (Pb) concentration ranged from 0.62 – 0.75 mg/kg in the soil sample, while cadmium (Cd) concentration ranged from 0.003 – 0.04 mg/kg. The soil was grossly polluted with hydrocarbon, with total petroleum content ranging from 15.3 – 62.5 mg/l. Extent of petroleum pollution varied greatly across the studied area, representing various degrees of oil activities. Wastewater samples collected from the study site showed gross hydrocarbon pollution. Total petroleum hydrocarbon in the wastewater ranged from 7.7 – 17.8 mg/l as against the permissible limit of 0.05ppm for unpolluted water. The Pb and Cd concentrations were 6 times and 4 times above the recommended threshold of 0.01 and 0.005 respectively, while Ni is 8 times above the threshold of 0.02 mg/l. These results necessitate urgent remediation efforts to mitigate environmental risks and protect public health. Continued monitoring and assessment are recommended to ensure compliance with environmental standards and promote sustainable soil water resources management practices.

Keywords: *Egbema, Heavy metal, Hydrocarbon, Wastewater, Pollution*

Introduction

Water resources worldwide are being depleted at a fast rate and the added pressure from pollution, growing demand and climate change is not desirable. According to Egbuikwem *et al.* (2021), pollution and increasing water demand, especially for agriculture, put severe pressure on freshwater sources, as a result there is progressive deficit to global water supply and severe water scarcity projections in years to come. With the rapid population growth, rapid industrial development and agricultural activities, freshwater sources are seriously impacted. This may lead to water scarcity. Wastewater produce physical, chemical and biological pollution that pose ecological and health hazards. It also creates scarcity of freshwater.

Oil spill on agricultural soils affects soil chemical, physical and biological properties. According to Okon and Ekpo (2022), crude-oil spillage destroys the biological components of the soil, alters soil chemicals, and makes the soil toxic and unproductive. Changes in soil qualities as a result of pollution from petroleum-derived substances can cause depletion in the amount of available nitrogen and phosphorus as well as shortage of water and oxygen in the soil (Ahmed and Fakhrudin, 2018).

Contamination of soil and water by crude oil spillage are largely by Polycyclic Aromatic

Hydrocarbons (PAH). PAH are toxic chemicals that occur in crude oil, gasoline and coal. These chemicals mix with the water to become wastewater and contaminate both the soil and the water. It will be beneficial if the contaminated water can be treated and reused for agricultural activities in the event that the water cannot be directly consumed by human beings and animals. By so doing, this will alleviate the pressure on freshwater.

Wastewater management is a critical component of environmental protection, particularly in communities affected by industrial activities. The Egbema Community has been identified as vulnerable to pollution due to nearby petroleum extraction operations. These activities can lead to the release of harmful substances into the water supply, posing risks to public health and local ecosystems. Understanding the sources and impacts of wastewater is essential for developing effective treatment and management strategies.

This study aims to determine the level of soil contamination from oil-producing activities. It also aims to investigate the wastewater quality discharged into nearby waterbody in oil-polluted environment of Egbema, Southeast Nigeria. This is with a view to designing suitable treatment method(s) that will allow the reuse of the treated waste/contaminated water for irrigation purpose.

Materials and Methods

Description of Study Area

This study was carried out in Egbema, Southeast Nigeria. Egbema lies in lowland area of southeastern Nigeria. The area is located between latitudes 5° 20'– 5° 40' N and longitudes 6° 40' – 6° 47' E, with mean annual rainfall and temperature ranges of 2450–2500 mm and 26.5–27.5° C respectively (Uzoho and Okechukwu, 2014). As reported in Uzoho and Okechukwu (2014), the geology of the area is made of quaternary, alluvium, wooded fresh water swamps and the Sombreiro-Warri Deltaic plains with deposits of petroleum and natural gas, and vegetation primarily of cassava (*Manihot esculentum*), oil palm (*Elaeis guineensis*) and bamboos (*Bambusa vulgaris*), while major economic activities are trading, farming, fishing, and oil exploitation.

Sample Collection and Preparation

The study involved collection and analysis of both soil and polluted water samples from the study area.

For soil sampling, samples were collected from four (4) different locations polluted by crude oil processing activities, in a completely randomized design. In each sampling location, duplicate samples were collected at 0-15 cm depth using a soil auger. The samples were then homogenized

thoroughly to give a composite soil samples as a representation of each location. Soil sample from each location was kept in a black polythene bag and properly labelled. The samples were subsequently transported to the laboratory, air dried, crushed and sieved using a 2 mm mesh sieve in preparatory for laboratory analysis of the selected soil properties.

For the wastewater sampling, samples were collected from two (2) identified point-source pollution sources by the river bank within the catchment of the oil-producing facilities. The samples were collected in sterilized plastic containers, properly labeled, and transported to the laboratory in ice-packed container for subsequent analysis to prevent chemical and biological transformation. However, the sampling was carried out on a rainy day, resulting in the mixing of the wastewater with runoff water.

Determination of Selected Soil and Wastewater Properties

pH of the soil was determined using a 1:2.5 soil to water paste and the glass electrode pH meter (FAO, 2021), organic carbon by Walkely and Black's oxidation method as described by Nelson and Sommers (1996). Particle size distribution was determined using Bouyoucous hydrometer method (Gee *et al.*, 2002). The heavy metals were extracted using wet acid digestion method and the filtrate were analyzed using standard

Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) procedures. Sodium and magnesium concentrations were determined by flame emission spectrophotometer according to Atkinson (2012)..

pH of the wastewater samples was analyzed using potentiometric method (APHA, 2023), total dissolved solids (TDS) and total suspended solids (TSS) using gravimetric method, sulphate, chemical oxygen demand (COD), calcium, magnesium, phosphate, nitrate, potassium, sodium, phosphorus, total organic carbon (TOC). Lead, cadmium, boron were determined using atomic absorption spectrometry, while total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) was determined using Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater (5520F), and total coliform was determined using spread plate method (APHA 2023, part 9221).

Palin test photometer was used with colorimetric method to determine the following: NO_3^- , SO_4^{2-} and Na^+ . Calcium (Ca^{2+}) and Magnesium (Mg^{2+})

were determined by Atomic Adsorption Spectrophotometer (ASS), while potassium was determined by flame photometry. Phosphorus was determined by the method described by (Bray and Kurtz, 1945).

COD was determined using titrimetric method (APHA, 2023), chloride was determined by Mohr's method (Shukla and Arya, 2018) and nitrate was determined by colorimetric method. Technicon auto analyzer flame photometer (IV) was used in determination of Sodium and potassium while calcium and magnesium was determined by EDTA titrimetric method (APHA, 2023, part 3500B).

Statistical Analysis

The results were analyzed using the mean, standard deviation, and coefficient of variation C_v to determine the extent of variability of parameters across the sampled locations.

Results and Discussion

Results of Soil Analysis

Table 1 Results of selected parameters from crude oil polluted soils in Egbema

Parameters	Location			
	A	B	C	D
pH	3.98	3.79	3.8	3.7
Total organic carbon, % TOC	39.26	40.33	28.84	27.84
Total Petroleum Content, mg/l	62.49	59.42	17.23	15.25
Magnesium, mg/kg Mg	3.52	2.52	2.52	2.52
Sodium ,mg/kg Na	0.31	0.21	0.51	0.52
Lead, mg/kg Pb	0.75	0.65	0.66	0.62
Cadmium, mg/kg Cd	0.04	0.04	0.003	0.003

Nickel, mg/kg Ni	0.08	0.09	0.11	0.1
Cobalt, mg/kg Co	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.06
Boron, mg/kg B	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.09
Clay, %	45.91	45.97	77.66	77.54
Sandy, %	54.07	53.99	22.3	22.38
Silt, %	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.08
Textural Class	Sandy clay	Sandy clay	Clay loam	Clay loam

Results of analysis of soil samples across the various sampled locations are presented in Table 1. Table 1 shows that pH of the soils is acidic, and ranged from 3.7–3.98 across the sampled locations. This value is below the threshold recommended by the Federal Ministry of Environment National Environmental Regulation (FMEnv) and the Canadian Soil Quality

Guideline (CSQG, 2007) of pH value of 6–8 for agricultural land. The soil pH portrays the extent of soil acidity or alkalinity. It is also used as an indicator for soil health and possible pollution sources. The observed pH values in the study location are clear indication of pollution from oil activities as suggested by the findings of Osuagwu and Olaifa (2018). Soil acidity reduces base cations required for plant growth and may result in phytotoxic concentrations of soluble aluminum (Enesiet *al.*, 2023).

Soil samples collected at the 0–15cm depth from the sampled locations showed that there was a

higher amount of sand (54%) than clay (46%) and very low silt fraction in locations A and B, while locations C and D witnessed much higher clay fractions (77%) compared to sand (22.4%) and silt is almost non-existent. It is likely that high clay fraction witnessed in locations C and D of the study area implies the act of pollution from oil and interferences with the normal compositions of soil, as observed by Eyetan and Ozabor (2021).

Total petroleum hydrocarbon varied greatly across the sampled locations. It ranged from 15.3 mg/l in location D to 62.5 mg/l in location A. This variation shows the degree of soil pollution from crude oil activities in the study area. The values of nickel and cadmium recorded across the sampled locations fell below the FMEnv guideline values of <1.00 and 0.1 mg/kg respectively, and therefore did not pose any significant risk on the environment. However, lead (Pb) ranged from 0.62 mg/kg in location D to 0.75 mg/kg in location A. These values exceed the recommended 0.05 mg/kg value set by FMEnv standard.

Statistical Analysis of Soil Parameters

Table 2 Statistical results of soil analysis

Parameters	Location				Mean (\bar{X})	Std. Dev. (σ)	$C_v = \frac{\sigma}{\bar{X}}$
	A	B	C	D			
pH	3.98	3.79	3.8	3.7	3.82	0.12	0.03
Total organic carbon, % TOC	39.26	40.33	28.84	27.84	34.07	6.64	0.19
Total Petroleum Content, mg/l	62.49	59.42	17.23	15.25	38.60	25.86	0.67
Magnesium, mg/kg Mg	3.52	2.52	2.52	2.52	2.77	0.50	0.18
Sodium ,mg/kg Na	0.31	0.21	0.51	0.52	0.39	0.15	0.39
Lead, mg/kg Pb	0.75	0.65	0.66	0.62	0.67	0.06	0.08
Cadmium, mg/kg Cd	0.04	0.04	0.003	0.003	0.02	0.02	0.99
Nickel, mg/kg Ni	0.08	0.09	0.11	0.1	0.10	0.01	0.14
Cobalt, mg/kg Co	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.06	0.03	0.02	0.95
Boron, mg/kg B	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.09	0.03	0.04	1.19
Clay, %	45.91	45.97	77.66	77.54	61.77	18.28	0.30
Sandy, %	54.07	53.99	22.3	22.38	38.19	18.30	0.48
Silt, %	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.08	0.05	0.03	0.56
Textural Class	Sandy clay	Sandy clay	Clay loam	Clay loam			

Table 2 shows the results of statistical analysis of soil parameters. The coefficient of variation of the samples show that pH was fairly the same across all locations ($C_v = 0.03$), while high

variability was observed among the various soil fractions ($C_v = 0.3-0.56$), indicating possible human disturbance over time. There was also high variability in the levels of cadmium and total petroleum content, with C_v of 0.99 and 0.19 respectively, as indicated in Table 1.

Results of Wastewater Analysis

Table 3 Results of selected parameters from point-source wastewater contamination in Egbema

Parameters	Location	
	1	2
pH	5.3	5.0
Total Dissolved Solid, mg/l TDS	12.0	10.4
Conductivity, $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$	18.5	16.0
Dissolved Oxygen m/l, DO	7.0	6.5
Total Suspended Solid, , mg/l TSS	1675.0	1211.1
Chemical Oxyen Demand, ,mg/l COD	2840.0	1576.0
Biological Oxygen Demand mg/l BOD ₅	4.6	3.3
Calcium, mg/l Ca ²⁺	4.1	4.84
Magnesium, mg/l Mg ²⁺	1.9	5.4
Phosphorus, mg/l P	39.3	16.7
Nitrate , mg/l NO ₃ ⁻	11.1	9.6
Phosphate, mg/l PO ₄ ³⁻	120.4	51.3
Potassium, mg/l K ⁺	22.5	17.5
Sodium, mg/l Na	0.2	0.03
Nickel, mg/l Ni	0.2	0.08
Lead, mg/l Pb	0.06	0.06
Cadmium, mg/l Cd	0.05	0.02
Cobalt, mg/l Co	0.01	0.04
TPH, mg/l	17.8	7.7

Table 3 shows results of selected parameters of the wastewater from oil facilities at point of discharge (point-source) to the river. The samples are acidic (pH range of 5.0 – 5.3) with TDS value of 10.4 – 12.0 mg/l. The pH values as observed in this study fell below the limits (6.5 – 9.7) recommended by the World Health Organization standards for effluents prior to their discharge to the waterbodies (WHO, 2006). The pH level indicates that the wastewater will likely have a negative influence on the receiving water body based on the pH. The largest variety of aquatic animals prefer a pH in the range of 6.5 – 8.5, and when the pH is outside this range,

diversity within the water body may decrease due to physiological stresses and reduced reproduction (Ibisiet *al.*, 2017). The pH of the water can be linked to the presence of dissolved salts of some metals in the water. BOD₅ ranged from 3.3 – 4.6 mg/l as against the high COD concentration of 1576.0 – 2840.0 mg/l. BOD is the measure of amount of oxygen needed to oxidize the organic matter contained in the sample through the activities of microorganism present in a sample of water. The test is the most widely used parameter of organic pollution applied to both surface and wastewater.

The low BOD can be attributed to the low organic constituents in the wastewater as compared to the high volume of its inorganic constituent, as depicted by the high COD value. The BOD and COD values are more than the recommended 1.0 and 40 mg/l threshold respectively recommended by the WHO for effluent discharge to surface water. Hence, this effluent constitute significant pollution source to the surface water. The concentration of TSS was high (1211.1 – 1675.0 mg/l), and multiple times more than the 30 mg/l recommended by the WHO. Total suspended solid (TSS) expresses the amount of suspended matter in the sample. According to Ibsi *et al.* (2017), the measurement of total solids can be useful as an indicator of the effects of runoff from urban and agricultural areas. The high TSS value recorded in this study could partly be contributed by runoff water which must have mixed with the wastewater during the sampling.

The results in Table 2 also revealed that the total petroleum hydrocarbon (TPH) ranged from 7.7 – 17.8 mg/l as against the permissible limit of 0.05ppm for unpolluted water (FEPA, 1991). The high level of TPH in the wastewater means that the sample contained substantial amount of untreated hydrocarbon waste which constitutes significant environmental hazards. When released into water body, oil destroys much of the aquatic lives by limiting oxygen transfer.

Among the heavy metals present in the sampled wastewater, Pb showed average value of 0.06 mg/l, Cd was <0.1, while Co and Ni concentrations ranged from 0.01 – 0.04 and 0.08 – 0.2 mg/l respectively. These values are typical of concentrations reported in literature for the respective heavy metals (e.g. Salem and Thiemann, 2022). However, comparing these values with FMEnv regulation on effluent quality for fisheries and recreational purpose, Pb and Cd are 6 times and 4 times above the recommended threshold respectively, while Ni is 8 times above the threshold.

While sodium concentration is within the threshold for effluent discharge, nitrate concentrations of 9.6 – 11.1 mg/l is above the threshold of 9.1 mg/l for effluent discharge for fisheries and recreational purpose (FMEnv, 2011).

Conclusion

Results of this work suggest that the community exhibits considerable contamination, posing serious environmental risks. These results necessitate urgent remediation efforts to mitigate environmental risks and protect public health. Immediate remediation measures are required to address the pollution and protect public health and local ecosystems. Continued monitoring and assessment are recommended to ensure

compliance with environmental standards and promote sustainable soil management practices.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by Tertiary Education Trust Fund (Tetfund) under its Institution based research (IBR) grant for 2022, awarded to the University of Agriculture and environmental Sciences (UAES) Umuagwo, Imo State.

References

- Ahmed, F. and Fakhruddin, A. N. M. (2018). A review on environmental contamination of petroleum hydrocarbons and its biodegradation. *International Journal of Environmental Sciences and Natural Resources*, 11(3), 1-7.
- APHA (2023) Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and Wastewater. 23rd Edition, American Public Health Association/American Water Works Association/Water Environment Federation, Washington DC, part 2310 B, 1-3.
- Atkinson, D. B. (2012). Determination of Calcium, Magnesium, and Sodium by Flame Atomic Spectrophotometry. Portland State University. pp.1-6. Online. Available at: <https://web.pdx.edu/~atkinsdb/teach/427/Expt-AtomicSpec.pdf>
- Bray, R. H. and Kurtz, L. T. (1945). Determination of total, organic, and available forms of phosphorus in soils. *Soil Sci.* 59, 39- 45.
- CSQG (2007). *Canadian Soil Quality Guidelines for the Protection of Environmental and Human Health*. Canadian Council of Ministers of the Environment, Winnipeg, P.4
- Egbuikwem, P. N., Obiechefu, G.C., Hai, F.I., Davenadera, M. C. E., Devendra, P. S. (2021). Potential of suspended growth biological processes for mixed wastewater reclamation and reuse in agriculture: challenges and opportunities. *Environmental Technology Review* 10(1), 77 – 110.
- Enesi, R. O., Dyck, M., Chang, S., Thilakarathna, M. S., Fan, X., Strelkov, S. and Gorim, L. Y. (2023). Liming remediates soil acidity and improves crop yield and profitability- a meta- analysis. *Front. Agron.* 5:1194896. doi: 10.3389/fagro.2023.1194896.
- Eyetan, T. and Ozabor, F. (2021). Oil spills deposits effect on soil physicochemical properties in Port Harcourt metropolis: Implication for agricultural planning. *Journal of Management and Social Science Research*, 2 (1/2), 45 – 58.
- FAO (2021). *Standard operating procedure for soil pH determination*. Rome, pp. 8-11.
- FEPA (1991) Standard range of heavy metals in sediment. Guidelines and standard for environmental pollution control in Nigeria 6:70 – 71
- FMEEnv (2011). National Environmental Regulations 2011. Federal Ministry of Environment, Abuja, P. B723-725.
- Ibisi, N., Ojo, M. and Ano A. O. (2017). Effects of Crude oil spills on Surface water in Niger- Delta Region of Nigeria. *American Journal of Engineering Research*, 5(5), 210-216.
- Nelson, D. W and Sommers, L. E. (1996). Methods of Soil Analysis. Part 3. Chemical Methods. *Soil Science Society of America Book Series* no.5, pp. 961-1010.
- Okon, U. and Ekpo, N. T. (2022). A review on effects of oil spillage on farmlands and implications for agricultural education in

Akwabom state. *Asia-Africa Journal of Agriculture*, 1, 29-41.

Osuagwu, E. S. and Olaifa, E. (2018). Effects of oil spills on fish production in the Niger Delta. *PloS one*, 13(10), e0205114.

Pomares, F., Baixauli, C., Aguilar, J.M., Giner, A., Tarazona, F., Gómez, J., Albiach, R. (2004). Effects of water and nitrogen fertilization on seed-grown globe artichoke. *ActaHortic.* 660, 303–309.

Salem, F and Thiemann, T. (2022). Produced Water from Oil and Gas Exploration—Problems, Solutions and Opportunities. *Journal of Water Resource and Protection*, 14, 142-185.

Shukla, M. and Arya, S. (2018). Determination of Chloride Ion (Cl⁻) Concentration in Ganga River Water by Mohr Method at Kanpur, India. *Green Chemistry & Technology Letters*, Vol 4, No 1, pp 06-08.

Uzoho, B. U. and Okechukwu, T. Y. (2014). Soil Organic Matter Distribution of Contrasting Landscapes in Egbema, Southeastern Nigeria. *Journal of Biology, Agriculture and Healthcare*, Vol.4, No. 7, 104-112.